

The halal label Morocco and the commitment of the Moroccan consumer on the national market

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Abstract: The objective of this paper is to study the influence of the cognitive perception of the Moroccan halal label LHM on the commitment of the Moroccan consumer towards the products labeled by the LHM. For this purpose, a questionnaire survey was conducted with a sample of 84 Moroccan consumers. A structural equation analysis using the Partial Least Squares approach by SmartPLS was performed. The results achieved indicate, on the one hand, that knowledge and trust have no influence on consumer commitment to the products labeled by the LHM. On the other hand, the consumer's sustained involvement has a positive influence on his commitment to the products labeled by the LHM.

Keywords: Knowledge, trust, sustainable involvement, commitment, label halal.

1. INTRODUCTION

Literally, the term “hala” refers to everything that is lawful, permissible or allowed for the Muslim. It generally refers to foods that are permitted to the faithful. On the contrary, it is opposed to what is “haram” or anything that is illicit or forbidden to Muslims, such as pork (which is very strongly disliked) and alcoholic beverages. And therefore, a halal product is defined as a safe product that does not contain any non-halal ingredients, manufactured and processed using equipment that has not been contaminated by non-halal elements, while complying with strict conditions in accordance with the requirements of hygiene, purity, health and according to the Islamic rite. Especially that the consumer whether Muslim or non-Muslim has become aware that halal is not only the way Muslims slaughter their animals, but halal is also about the environment, sustainability, animal welfare and food safety (Golnaz, et al., 2010).

On the global aspect, we find that the global halal market is spreading over several food and non-food products (such as cosmetics) as well as it is spreading over halal services such as hotel services. This wide positioning of halal products and services can be reflected by the increasing Muslim populations in the world, as well as the high attention from consumers, producers and regulators towards halal products (Rahim and Shahwan, 2013). On the regulatory aspect, the emergence of the global halal market has led to the drafting, realization and publication of a global halal standard allowing the free movement of halal products through the possession of a commercial instrument called halal label aimed at protecting the national market and penetrating new markets (Bergeaud-Blackler, 2006).

On the national aspect, Morocco has been interested in the halal industry since 2012 through the commitment of its standards institute IMANOR in the establishment of a Halal Morocco Label (LHM) aimed at presenting the necessary guarantees to Moroccan companies to protect the consumer as well as to gain his trust, his commitment and his lasting involvement with the products labeled by LHM.

Indeed, for products labeled halal, researchers have been more interested in the commitment of the Muslim consumer in relation to existing halal products on the markets of non-Islamic countries. The latter seek to consolidate their halal markets following a combination of economic, religious and political reasons (Bergeaud-Blackler, 2005). This market consolidation is becoming a necessity where the issue of halal certification still suffers from the problem of labeling and traceability in the food circuit. On the contrary, and in Islamic countries where the product is halal by default. A halal label is not only a purely religious issue (Hamzaee and Ramezani, 2011), as well as religion is not the only reason for halal consumption (Bergeaud-Blackler and Bonne, 2006). In another way, it is not only related to the taboo of pork and alcoholic drinks. But it extends to the hygienic and sanitary side in the way of preserving, treating or circulating such halal product. However, a Malaysian study suggests that awareness of halal-labeled products among Muslim consumers is influenced by their knowledge and understanding of halal concepts (Ahmad, Abaidah, & Yahya, 2013), whereas this is an Islamic country where products are halal by default and there is previously a religious obligation to consume halal-labeled products. This may highlight that the study on the perception of halal products among Muslim consumers fluctuates between Islamic and non-Islamic countries, as well as existing work in this direction often focuses on the immigrant population in non-Islamic countries. As a result, our understanding of the cognitive conception of the halal label among Muslim consumers in an Islamic country like Morocco is still insufficient. Thus, the results cannot be generalized. In this regard, we decided to fill this gap and focus on studying the cognitive perception of the LHM among Moroccan consumers and consequently, its influence on their engagement with LHM labeled products.

In a concrete way, our research problem can be summarized by the following question:

What is the influence of the cognitive perception of the LHM on the Moroccan consumer's commitment to products labeled by the LHM?

The objective of our research is therefore to propose a conceptual framework that links the cognitive dimensions of the LHM with the commitment of the Moroccan consumer. More specifically, we will try to weave the degree of the Moroccan consumer's knowledge of the LHM as well as his trust, commitment and sustainable involvement in front of the LHM labeled products. Furthermore, we will try to examine the causality between the four concepts in order to know if there is a cognitive perception on the part of the consumer in front of halal labeled products in Morocco.

Our research is structured in three parts. We will begin with a review of the literature in order to highlight the main concepts used and to provide a theoretical basis for the various hypotheses formulated. Then, we will present the methodology of our research. This part will be followed by the main results obtained and a discussion of these results. Finally, we will end our study with a conclusion mentioning the main contributions of our study, as well as the future research directions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A. Knowledge of and commitment to the products labeled by the LHM

A label is a logo affixed to the packaging of a product to inform the consumer that the said product meets a set of criteria defined in the specifications of the label, as well as that it meets the specific requirements of the consumer according to its credibility to be issued by a certification body approved by the state. In the same context, the halal logo is defined as an authoritative, independent and reliable testimony to support halal food claims (Hamzaee and Ramezani, 2011). D'Souza (2004) states that the objective of the label is to reduce information asymmetry and consumer uncertainty. Hence, the need to have the correct information and accurate knowledge at the time of purchase or use of the labeled product.

In fact, knowledge is a simple concept that can be defined by what individuals perceive that they know (Brucks, 1985). According to this definition, and within the framework of the relationship between product and consumer, we can define knowledge as the perception of the set of information collected and stored by the consumer on a product either at the time of purchase or at the time of use, this cognitive perception can guide or orient the consumer at the time of purchase and influence him in the choice of such or such a product which can effect on his commitment towards a precise product.

However, the knowledge of a label does not necessarily reflect the preference or choice of a certain product where the sign of the label is opposite on its packaging. Indeed and as an example, a consumer can be well informed about organic products characterized by the sign bio and besides that they are good for his health, it can be that he does not prefer them because of different reasons related to the price, the quantity or the suspicion. The same goes for products labeled halal. A consumer may consider well-informed about everything related to the LHM, but he is not cognitively or morally obliged to give special importance to the products labeled by the LHM. And consequently, the knowledge and the commitment even they can weave a link of causality by the means that one cannot commit to a product if one does not know it. Both concepts are suspected to reach this causal link as a result of the decisional gap between knowledge and commitment.

Based on this reasoning, we can advance our hypothesis as follows:

H1: Knowledge of the LHM positively influences consumer engagement with the products labeled by the LHM.

B. Trust and commitment to the products labeled by the LHM

Numerous research studies have highlighted the amplitude and diversity of definitions of trust. Consequently, the polymorphism of this concept has hindered the development of researchers in this field (Guibert, 1999). In the literature, and according to Chouk and Parrien (2003), we find that trust sometimes takes on psychological amplitude allowing for a cognitive and affective dimension, and at other times, it is apprehended as an action translating a trusting behavior or a behavioral intention translating into a willingness to be vulnerable. In this respect, the notion of trust and the emotional character always remain linked and materialized by benevolence (effective component) and credibility (cognitive component). While this relationship is ensured as a relational approach as well as based on an expectation with emotional connotation articulated around two components: credibility and benevolence (Graf, et al., 1999). According to this work, we find that trust as a composite concept is defined from the consumer's point of view, as a psychological variable reflecting a set of accumulated presumptions about the credibility, integrity and benevolence that the consumer attributes to a product (Gurviez and Korchia, 2002).

In addition to the above and in several researches, commitment is defined as the consequence of trust in the consumer-product relationship. Indeed, one cannot commit to a product if there is not at least a minimum of trust in it. In the same context, we find that trust in the label is based essentially on the credibility that the consumer attributes to the logo of this label. The latter is considered to be one of the crucial elements of marketing effectiveness (Larceneuw, 2004). Indeed, trust in the halal label in an Islamic country may be outdated or its evolution misunderstood because a consumer residing in an Islamic country is implicitly and preliminarily certain that the product is halal per se. While halal has gone beyond the religious aspect and has become a guarantee for positive benefits for the mental, spiritual and physical health of the consumer (Arif and Sidek, 2015). From another angle, Malaysian studies defend and accentuate the trust towards the JAKIM label by Malaysian consumers who rely heavily on their trusted institution JAKIM (Ahmad, Abaidah, & Yahya, 2013), while it is a country with a dominant Muslim population.

Based on this reasoning, we can advance our hypothesis as follows:

H2: Trust in the LHM positively influences consumer engagement with the products labeled by the LHM.

C. Sustainable involvement with the products labeled by the LHM

According to Strazzieri (1994), the problem of confusion in the term sustainable involvement stems from the fact that it is used to designate such different phenomena. And therefore, we are exclusively interested here in the consumer's sustainable involvement with a specific product (to be labeled by the LHM). In this respect, we find that the consumer's sustainable involvement with a product can be translated by several conscious and unconscious reasons, as well as it can depend on an affective/cognitive or sustainable/contextual approach (Miled-Chérif, 2001). We are talking about a state that reflects the amount of interest, relevance and attachment that a particular consumer has for the product. This is obviously the case for the PIA (Relevance, Interest and Attachment) scale, which represents the most purified conception of sustainable involvement in the face of the heterogeneity of approaches to involvement and the diversity of instruments that can measure it (Strazzieri, 1994; Le Roux, et al., 1997; Miled-Chérif, 2001).

In the context of cognitive perception of sustainable involvement, the product may be preferable to a consumer by its functional attributes or by its importance in meeting an explicitly logical need. While the affective aspect may make the product important through the consumer's emotional appeal and personal intuition to provide some implicit or explicitly expressed pleasure.

If we focus on the relationship that may exist between involvement and commitment, we find that the two concepts are considered as two distinct notions: The higher the involvement, the higher the commitment (Miled-Chérif, 2001). If the consumer is highly involved and has been satisfied with his purchases, his commitment will translate into product loyalty. If not, he will continue his search and change other products. In this respect, a product is in a stable position in the market when it is preferred by highly committed buyers.

Based on this reasoning, we can advance our hypothesis as follows:

H3: The consumer's sustainable involvement positively influences their commitment to the products labeled by the LHM.

Based on these different hypotheses, we can propose in Fig. 1 the conceptual model of our research as follows:

Figure1. Conceptual research model

Source : Author

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This second part focuses on the choice and description of the sample studied the development of the questionnaire and the statistical method chosen.

A. The measurements of the constructs

For the scale measuring the knowledge variable, we chose the work of Flynn and Goldsmith (1999), whose scale was reduced to 5 items, whereas it originally contained 9, with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of up to 0,93. As for the scale for measuring the variable trust, we chose the Gurviez and Korchia (2002) scale, which covers three dimensions: credibility, integrity and benevolence. This scale was reduced to 8 items from the original 14, and we eliminated 1 item from the integrity dimension because it was not significant in the context of our study. Then, it was tested empirically in the work of Gurviez and Korchia (2003) and it gave satisfaction with a coefficient alpha of Cronbach going up to 0,948. Next, the scale for measuring the sustainable involvement variable was developed from the work of Strazzieri (1994) based on three dimensions: relevance, interest and attraction. With 6 items, the same initially validated scale was empirically tested in the work of Le Roux et al (1997) and it gave satisfaction with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of up to 0,87. Finally, the scale for measuring the commitment variable was developed and empirically tested in the work of Le Roux et al (1997) with 3 items giving satisfaction with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient equal to 0,87. The same scale, initially designed and validated, was adapted by Gurviez and Korchia (2002) and (2003) in their work, giving internal reliability coefficients greater than 0,8. The table I shows the measurement scales used in our study.

TABLE I. SCALES OF MEASUREMENT USED

Variables et authors		Items
Knowledge (Flynn et Goldsmith, 1999)		I consider myself very well-informed about all things LHM
		In my social circle, I am one of those who know the most about the LHM
		I know a little about LHM
		Compared to most other people, I know less about what relates to the LHM
		I really don't know much about the LHM
Trust (Gurviez et Korchia, 2002) et (Gurviez et Korchia, 2003)	Credibility	The LHM make me feel safe
		I trust the quality of the products labeled by the LHM
		Buying products labeled by the LHM is a guarantee
	Integrity	The LHM is sincere with its customers
		The LHM expresses an interest in its customers
	Benevolence	I think that LHM is renewing its products to reflect advances in research
I think that the LHM is always looking to improve its response to consumer needs		
Sustainable involvement (Le Roux, et al., 1997) et (Strazzieri, 1994)	Relevance	The product labeled by the LHM is very important to me
		I attach particular importance to the product labeled by the LHM
	Interest	I particularly like to talk about the product labeled by the LHM
		I am interested in a product labeled by the LHM
	Attraction	I feel particularly attracted to the product labeled by the LHM
		I enjoy learning about a product labeled by the LHM

Commitment (Le Roux, et al., 1997) et (Gurviez et Korchia, 2002) et (Gurviez et Korchia, 2003)	If necessary, I would make a few small sacrifices in order to continue using the products labeled by the LHM
	I tend to praise and defend the products labeled by the LHM
	I think that I will appreciate LHM products for a long time to come

Source : Author

All items are rated on a Likert scale of 1 to 5 from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". The questionnaire also contains a section for socio-demographic data. Also, given that the measurement scale for the knowledge variable used is in English, it was also very important to translate it into French while keeping the same meaning for all the items. Then, we opted for a pre-test of our questionnaire with a chartered accountant and a group of 4 PhD students. Based on their comments, we were able to modify, simplify and rectify certain questions that were poorly expressed and difficult to understand. Finally, we were able to have the final version of our questionnaire.

B. Choice of the sample

Given that our database includes Moroccan consumers based on all the regions of the kingdom as well as the arrival to them and address them a questionnaire is difficult especially as our study is conducted during the period of the pandemic COVID-19. For this, our study is carried out remotely while using Facebook and LinkedIn groups that take on the consumption and recommendation of products and services on the Moroccan territory. As well as groups of young Moroccan students and PhD students. And this through the frequent presence of Moroccan citizens on social networks especially during the pandemic and generally by the increase of internet use by Moroccan internet users.

In this respect, the convenience sample was a justified alternative for us, as well as the administration of the questionnaire was done online by using Google Forms. This mode allowed us to save time, to have almost no financial cost and most importantly to keep the sanitary security by social distancing. The number of responses received in the first instance was 210, of which 84 were usable. This represents an acceptable response rate of 40%. A description of the characteristics of our respondents and their distribution by region of residence are presented in the table II and Fig. 2 below:

TABLE II. DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Characteristics of respondents	Number des respondents	Percentage
<i>Gender :</i>		
• Male	• 34	• 40,5
• Female	• 50	• 59,5
<i>Age :</i>		
• Under 20 years old	• 2	• 2,4
• Between 21 and 30 years old	• 44	• 52,4
• Between 31 and 40 years old	• 25	• 29,8
• Between 41 and 50 years old	• 11	• 13,1
• Over 51 years old	• 2	• 2,4
<i>level of study</i>		
• high school studies	• 3	• 3,6
• undergraduate studies	• 23	• 27,4
• Master studies	• 30	• 35,7
• PhD Student	• 28	• 33,3

Source : Author

Figure 2. Distribution of respondents by region of residence

C. The statistical analysis method used

We opted for structural equation modeling (SEM) to statistically analyze our model, the interest of the latter lies essentially in its capacity to test simultaneously the existence of causal relationships between several latent variables. For this reason, we chose the modeling by Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach since it is more suitable in case of obtaining a correct prediction of the level of the independent variables according to the dependent variables, as well as it is well adapted to exploratory type analysis in which the estimation can be carried out on small samples (Lacroux, 2011). In general, this approach is adapted to predictive causal analyses with a situation of high complexity and low theoretical information (Fernandes, 2012).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Exploratory factor analysis

In order to study the properties of each of the measurement scales as well as to evaluate their dimensionality, we used exploratory factor analysis as a tool to clean up the measurement scales used, especially since some of them are in English. To this end, we opted for principal component analysis (PCA). According to this method, we were able to extract the main factorial axes and to retain only the variables that have a factorial contribution higher than 0.5. To assess the reliability of the constructs, Cronbach's Alpha was mobilized by an acceptable value equal to or greater than 0.6 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). However, it was first necessary to ensure the factorability of the data, for which two statistical tests are possible: the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test, which must be greater than 0,6 ;and Bartlett's test of sphericity, which must tend towards zero.

The results obtained from the SPSS 25 software indicate that the Bartlett's Sphericity test is significant for all the selected factors. Also, the results show that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) index has a value that varies between 0,6 and 0,9, which exceeds the acceptable level of 0,6. Also, the results obtained indicate that all factor loadings exceed 0,5 with the exception of the three items for the knowledge variable (CONN3, CONN4 and CONN5). These items were removed and the PCA was run again in an iterative way. Next, Cronbach's Alpha was calculated for each variable, indicating that all the proposed constructs have good internal consistency and are therefore considered reliable. As shown in the table III below:

TABLE III. RESULTS OF THE EXPLORATORY FACTORIAL ANALYSIS

Constructs	Items	Factorability test	Variance	Loadings	Cronbach's alpha
Knowledge	CONN1	KMO : 0,611 χ^2 : 72,578 df : 10 p : 0,00	68,171	0,765	0,640
	CONN2			0,841	
Trust	CONF1	KMO : 0,913 χ^2 : 575,467 df : 21 p : 0,00	77,774	0,883	0,952
	CONF2			0,895	
	CONF3			0,871	
	CONF4			0,848	
	CONF5			0,896	
	CONF6			0,860	
	CONF7			0,724	
Sustainable involvement	IMMP1	KMO : 0,849 χ^2 : 455,038 df : 15 p : 0,00	75,688	0,834	0,935
	IMMP2			0,826	
	IMMP3			0,764	
	IMMP4			0,897	
	IMMP5			0,847	
	IMMP6			0,732	
Commitment	ENG1	KMO : 0,748 χ^2 : 167,103 df : 3 p : 0,00	84,780	0,937	0,910
	ENG2			0,918	
	ENG3			0,907	

Source : Author

B. Confirmatory factor analysis

- Measurement Model Test

This step allows us to assess the convergent and discriminant validity of the constructs retained during the exploratory analysis. Consequently, it represents an essential prerequisite to validate before proceeding to the hypothesis tests of our model. In this respect, we will first analyze the validity and reliability of our latent reflexive variables. This step will consist in evaluating for each variable: the convergent validity, also known as the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), which must be greater than 0,5 (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988) in order to be able to say that the construct has shared more than 50% of its variance with the measurement statements. Then the composite reliability (CR) which must be greater than 0,7 (Didellon and Valette-Florence, 1996). And finally, the factorial contributions (loadings) which must be greater than 0,5 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). The table IV confirms the reliability and convergent validity of the different constructs:

TABLE IV. RELIABILITY AND CONVERGENT VALIDITY

Constructs	Items	Loadings	CR	AVE
Knowledge	CONN1	0,988	0,791	0,668
	CONN2	0,599		
Trust	CONF1	0,905	0,961	0,778
	CONF2	0,896		
	CONF3	0,896		
	CONF4	0,894		
	CONF5	0,911		
	CONF6	0,888		
	CONF7	0,775		
Sustainable involvement	IMMP1	0,818	0,949	0,757
	IMMP2	0,873		
	IMMP3	0,816		
	IMMP4	0,933		
	IMMP5	0,935		
	IMMP6	0,836		
Commitment	ENG1	0,935	0,943	0,848
	ENG2	0,915		
	ENG3	0,912		

Source : Author

From Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) point of view, discriminant validity can be established if it does not include the value 1. And if we refer to the rules proposed by Fornell and Larcker (1981), we will find that discriminant validity is established if the variances extracted by each construct of the model and its indicators are greater than the variance shared between that construct and the other indicators. This indicates that the indicators have a stronger correlation with the latent variable they represent than with the other latent variables. The table V below shows that the discriminant validity of the constructs in our model is established.

TABLE V. DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY

	Trust	Knowledge	Commitment	Sustainable involvement
Trust	0,882			
Knowledge	0,197	0,817		
Commitment	0,728	0,242	0,921	
Sustainable involvement	0,850	0,340	0,833	0,870

Source : Author

▪ Hypothesis Testing

Before confirming or rejecting our hypotheses, we first needed to know the nature of the relationships between the latent explanatory variables and the latent variable being explained, which is what the structural model shows us. The validation of the latter is examined by the coefficient of determination R^2 , which gives us an overall idea of the fit of the model. In the Fig. 3 , the value of the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0,697$ which means that the explanatory variables participate strongly in the formation of the dependent variable according to the approach of Chin (1998) which ensures a sufficient explanatory power if the value R^2 is close to 0,670.

Figure 3. Measurement model test result (SmartPLS output)

In the same context, the verification of the absence of multi-collinearity between the explanatory variables is an essential step in the analysis of the structural model. In this respect, we use the Variance Inflation Factor

(VIF). The rule indicates that the absence of collinearity between the independent variables will be verified if the VIF is lower than the value 5. In our case study, the VIF values of all independent variables were also less than 5 (VIF of trust = 3,721, VIF of knowledge = 1,171 and finally the VIF of sustainable involvement = 4,044), which means that there was no multi-collinearity in our model.

In order to determine the predictive power of our model, we rely on the Q^2 coefficient. The rule indicates that the further the value of the latter is from 0, the greater the predictive reliability of the estimates of the construct (Stone, 1974). In our case of study, the value of Q^2 is 0,566 which means that our model has a very high predictive power.

In addition to all the above, we will now come to the test of our hypotheses. It is obviously a question of validating or rejecting each hypothesis, which depends on both: the T-Student values, which allow us to test the significance of the causal relations of our model and which must be greater than 1,64. And to the P-Value values which must be lower than 0,05 (5%) for all the structural coefficients (Path coefficient).

TABLE VI. RESULTS OF HYPOTHESIS TESTING

N°	Hypothesis	Path β	T-Student	P-Value	Decision
H1	Knowledge \rightarrow Commitment	-0,040	0,458	0,616	Rejected
H2	Trust \rightarrow Commitment	0,062	0,502	0,647	Rejected
H3	Sustainable involvement \rightarrow Commitment	0,794	6,574	0,000	Accepted

Source : Author

According to the table VI, the statistical results obtained from the H1 hypothesis indicate that student's T has a value of 0,458 which is not greater than 1,64, as well as the p-value that exceeds 5% (P-Value = 0,616). In this regard, the H1 hypothesis which indicates that knowledge of the LHM positively influences consumer commitment to LHM labeled products was rejected, and therefore, we can argue that the relationship between knowledge and commitment is not validated in the context of the Moroccan consumer.

The same case applies to the H2 hypothesis, student's T has a value of 0,502 less than 1,64, as well as P-Value = 0,647 a value that exceeds 5%. Thus, the H2 hypothesis that indicates that trust in the LHM positively influences consumer commitment to the products labeled by the LHM was rejected, and therefore, we can argue that the relationship between trust and commitment is not validated in the context of the Moroccan consumer.

For the last hypothesis H3 indicating that the consumer's sustainable involvement positively influences his commitment to the products labeled by the LHM was validated because the statistical results obtained indicate that student's T has a value of 6,574 which is greater than 1,64 and the structural link value which is 0,794, as well as the P-value which is less than 5%. Therefore, we can argue that the relationship between sustainable involvement and commitment is validated in the context of the Moroccan consumer.

5. CONCLUSION

The objective of our research study was to focus on the influence of consumer cognitive design on engagement with the products labeled by the LHM. Specifically, we wove together the degree of consumer knowledge of the LHM as well as consumer trust, sustainable involvement, and commitment to the products labeled by the LHM. In this regard, we focused on Moroccan consumers. This choice can be explained by the

reason of knowing the place of the LHM among Moroccan consumers on the national market, as well as whether the products labeled by the LHM take a share of the national market or they only benefit from the share of the export market.

Based on the existing literature, we completed a conceptual framework that encompasses the existing causal links between the variables in our model. The objective was to empirically test these relationships on a sample of 84 Moroccan consumers residing in all regions of the Moroccan kingdom. Then, the aim was to validate our conceptual model and consequently to have results and contributions that can contribute in the research on the halal market in Islamic countries like the case of Morocco.

On the theoretical aspect, our added value is formed in the sense that we have participated in the existing literatures of commitment, knowledge, trust and sustainable involvement of the consumer towards a labeled product, and this by examining the causal links between the commitment with all the other independent variables. Moreover, the choice of the LHM as a criterion in the products questioned in the context of Moroccan consumers was an initiative by us, something that has never been the subject of an empirical study in an Islamic and Arab territory like Morocco.

On the methodological aspect, we adapted some measurement scales and translated others from the foreign context to the Moroccan context based on the aspect of halal labeling. These scales have been purified to ensure their reliability and subsequently make them consistent with the context of our study. And why not to be used in future works on Islamic and Arabic territories.

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